

STAKEHOLDERS

- ARS - Réunion Regional Health Agency
- Sillages Association
- CCIR
- Chamber of Agriculture
- Departement Council
- DEAL Reunion
- Energies Réunion
- IRD
- Reunion Water Agency
- Réunion Region
- National representation
- ...

CHALLENGES

- Improve **pricing policies system** with local stakeholders
- Maintain the quality of **surface water**, fight against **saline untrusions**
- Need of **investment in infrastructures**

AMBITION

- Improve the **socio-economic performance** of local water pricing policies
- Improve the **vertical** (between stakeholders at different levels) and **horizontal** (between local stakeholders) **dialogues**
- Fostering the **co-construction** of public water policies, with a focus on the crossed sectors
- Improving the **citizen engagement** by providing **relevant socio-economic information and tools**

INN WATER PARTNERS

A **consortium** gathering 13 organisations (Research and Technology Organisations, SMEs, end users, associations with EU and international coverages).

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INN WATER

Promoting
social innovation
to renew
multi-level and cross-sector
water governance

Pilot Site #1

RÉUNION ISLAND
France

Led by

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RÉUNION ISLAND

Réunion Island is a French volcanic island located near Madagascar, in the western Indian Ocean. Covering an area of 2,500 km², it has a steep relief with a narrow coastal strip where a large part of the population is concentrated (75%).

METHOD

1. Set the composition of pilot site community
2. Assess the current water governance situation
3. Set objectives and planning
4. Test and implement schemes and tools
5. Feedback and assessment

5 PILOT SITES

Implementing different types of governance mechanisms and covering different **water challenges**, test and co-develop the tools and methods.

INN WATER
Pilot Site Community

France, Réunion Island - **Economic focus**

Italy, Middle Brenta Basin - **Ecosystem services & Drinking water sector**

Spain, Figueres - **Water scarcity**

United Kingdom, West Country - **Water quality**

Hungary, Middle Tisza - **Water allocation**

